

MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PHYSICS IN THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUING EDUCATION – PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. *The article presents a perspective of modern educational technologies in teaching Physics. Physics is the subject that requires a strong basic knowledge and practical expertise. Learning Physics is learning the physical phenomena occurring in the nature. Learning and finding the secrets of nature requires the study of literature. The major theme in learning Physics is the problem-solving skills along with basic knowledge of programming. Every concept in Physics should be taught as a solution to a specified problem. The concepts of Physics are used in the latest technologies such as Artificial Intelligence and machine learning, thereby creating a sophisticated life style to the human being. It is the prime responsibility of the teachers to provide the best quality of education with modern educational technologies to the next generation Physicists. In the present review article, the use of modern educational technologies in teaching Physics are discussed.*

Keywords: *Education, technology, Physics*

Introduction

Physics is the subject which is interconnected with industry and technology (1). The research of unsolved problems beginning from the exploration of the universe (2 & 3) to the latest advances in science and technology are discussed in Physics. There are so many unsolved problems which needs more efforts and intellectual minds. In order to find the solutions to such hidden and unsolved problems, a strong basic knowledge of Physics is mandatory. The smartness and intellectuality of a researcher cannot be built in days. It requires a lot of effort and guidance from their childhood. Hence, the basic requirement to become a good researcher will start from the school level.

Teaching Physics in India

In a country like India where the population is huge, it is not an easy task to provide sophisticated facilities to all the students at school level. Hence, corporate and private schools are also taking responsibility to develop the secondary education. The statistics of private and Government schools in India is well documented (4). The vision and mission of all the schools are almost similar but with different curriculum and different approaches. Especially in Physics, students are motivated in a proper way starting from learning the basics of Physics to the use of physics in advanced technologies. Especially in India, teaching physics is having a different approach. The top institutes for higher education in India are Indian Institute of Science and Indian Institute of Technologies, where all the world class laboratory facilities for doing good research are available. There are few IITs across the country and it is a dream for every student to get admission in these institutes. More than one million students are attempting the entrance examination every year. The competition is severe and the examination is very tricky. In order to get admission, the students have to prepare from their school level education. From grade 6, the students are trained for IIT entrance examination. The basic knowledge of the student in Basic

sciences like Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry is fundamentally tested in the IIT entrance examination. Every question will test the problem-solving ability of the students. Hence, from the school level, the Physics teachers are motivating the students towards the improvement of problem-solving skills. The system of education where every concept not only in physics but also in science, should be taught in a way to motivate the students towards framing the problem in the phenomenon and finding true solution to the problem. This is the way how the Indian students are succeeding and contributing their level best in the field of science and technology.

Latest technologies in teaching-learning process

Latest technologies such as mobile learning and digital content platforms, AI-powered learning environments (Chat GPT), Cloud computing, Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR), Gamification of learning, social media in learning, wearable technology, automated assessments, adaptive learning, mobile learning are used in educational institutes that are facilitating the students in learning everything whenever and wherever they need. EdTech is the latest technology popularly known as Education technology (5), is a method of integrating technology using ICT tools into the class room to build better teaching-learning experiences that result in higher learning outcomes.

Special Focus on unsolved problems in Physics

Global warming, Ozone layer depletion and Greenhouse effect are some of the major problems that are recognized as global issues and their remedies are to be discussed with the students. On the other hand, some unsolved problems in Physics such as Quantum Gravity, particle masses, the measurement problem, turbulence, dark energy, dark matter, complexity, the matter – antimatter asymmetry and the arrow of time (6) has to be necessarily discussed with the students from the school level so that the students will get an idea about how and why to read Physics.

The eminence of Physics teacher in the class room will play an important role in the Modern Educational technologies in teaching Physics in the system of continuing education and gives better results compared to traditional black board teaching. Few best practices of teaching Physics are discussed below.

- Prepare curriculum according to international standards
- Check whether the curriculum design contains application-oriented concepts and technology
- Motivate the students towards reading text books
- Distinguish the theoretical and experimental physics in a proper way
- Establish the laboratory facilities and monitor each and every student to perform the experiments independently.
- Classify the full session as two halves, the first half session for theory and the other half session for practical work
- Use models and charts for explanation of the concepts of Physics
- Use of smart boards and online sessions
- Frequent visit to the science center/national Research laboratories in and around the country
- Motivate the students towards science quiz/seminars and conferences
- Form Science clubs in the schools
- Update themselves and motivate the students towards solving the unsolved problems/issues/phenomena in Physics
- Differentiate the linearity theory (Quantum Physics) and the non-linearity theory (Classical Physics)

- Register in Research Gate and should have a thrust in learning the advances in Physics
- Maintain sophisticated library containing latest research articles and books for literature collection
- Inviting eminent Professors and Scientists to the schools and organizations to interact with the students
- Conduct knowledge exchange programs with other country students through online
- Frequently organize science exhibitions and science fairs in the schools
- Provide the bibliography and life styles of Physicists to the students etc.,

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